

1 Title page

2 **Title:**

3 **Valorisation of a lignin-rich residue via catalytic pyrolysis over ZrO₂/ZSM-5**
4 **technical catalyst**

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13 **Keywords:** lignin-rich residue, pyrolysis, bio-oil upgrading, oxygenated aromatics,
14 phenolics, ZSM-5

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19 **Abstract**

20 The thermochemical valorisation of a lignin-rich residue has been investigated by thermal
21 and catalytic pyrolysis. The catalyst, based on nanocrystalline ZSM-5, has been modified
22 with ZrO₂ and agglomerated with attapulgite (ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP). Firstly, the effect of
23 the temperature in thermal pyrolysis has been explored, establishing 600°C as the optimal
24 temperature to thermally decompose the lignin-rich feedstock, yielding 53.7 wt.% of bio-
25 oil* (water-free bio-oil). In contrast, the incorporation of the technical catalyst using an
26 ex-situ reactor, as well as the increase in the catalyst/lignin ratio, strongly affected the
27 mass and energy yields of products. Thus, a significant decrease of the bio-oil* yield was
28 observed, although its composition was significantly improved, with a reduction of the
29 oxygen content from 30 to 10 wt.%. Comparing the parent zeolite with the technical
30 catalyst, the latter afforded a bio-oil* production with lower oxygen content, a higher
31 share of aromatics and lower concentration of heavy species (non-detected by GC-MS).
32 In particular, the technical catalyst allows increasing the concentration in bio-oil* of GC-
33 MS detected compounds, which are the most valuable for commercial applications, by a
34 factor of 2.5 regarding the thermal test. Interestingly, these remarkable results are
35 obtained despite working under mild catalytic conditions (450°C, catalyst/lignin=0.2 g/g).

36 **Keywords:** lignin-rich residue, pyrolysis, bio-oil upgrading, oxygenated aromatics,
37 phenolics, ZSM-5

38 **1. Introduction**

39 Lignin is one of the three main components of lignocellulose, its content being dependent
40 on the type of biomass source: around 30 wt.% in softwood and 20-25 wt.% in hardwood
41 [1]. Lignin is considered a low-cost natural resource with a high potential for industrial
42 use, having a world production in 2015 around 100 million tonnes [2]. Lignin is an
43 amorphous natural polymer composed by three main phenylpropane monomeric units; p-
44 coumaryl, coniferyl and sinapyl alcohols [1,3–5]. Due to its structure, lignin is a
45 recalcitrant compound resistant to microbial and chemical attacks [6]. In contrast,
46 thermochemical processes have demonstrated to be able to disrupt the lignin structure.

47 Processing of lignocellulose in the paper pulp industry generates lignin-rich streams,
48 which are usually considered as a residue or a low-value co-product. In this way, the main
49 types of lignin correspond with different paper manufacturing processes: Kraft wood
50 delignification [3], sulphite pulping [7], soda pulping [8] and Organosolv pulping
51 processes [9].

52 On the other hand, lignin-rich residues are also obtained by a variety of lignocellulose
53 treatments aimed to increase its digestibility regarding the subsequent production of
54 bioethanol. Accordingly, a potential biorefinery approach for the overall valorisation of
55 the three biopolymers in lignocellulose could be based on the cascade combination of
56 chemical, biological and catalytic treatments, such as: i) steam explosion for the
57 hydrolysis of cellulose, ii) enzymatic hydrolysis of hemicellulose, and iii) conversion of
58 the final lignin-rich residue by catalytic pyrolysis. The benefits derived from the coupling
59 of biological and thermochemical processes have been shown in a recent work in which
60 the residue coming from bioethanol production was processed by thermal and catalytic
61 pyrolysis, leading to a remarkable enhancement of the overall yield into liquid biofuels
62 compared to single treatment approaches [10].

63 A variety of catalysts have been reported in the literature for the catalytic pyrolysis of
64 lignocellulosic feedstocks, such as zeolites (X [11], Y [11], Beta [12], mordenite [13] and
65 ZSM-5 [4,13–15]), metal oxides like MgO [16], TiO₂, CeO₂ or ZrO₂ [17,18], red mud
66 [14] and bifunctional catalysts [19]. Zeolitic catalysts, and in particular ZSM-5 zeolite,
67 are the most widely employed since their acidic sites promote several reactions
68 (deoxygenation, cracking, aromatisation, etc) that lead to commercially valuable
69 products, as it is the case of aromatic and olefinic hydrocarbons [20]. However, low bio-

70 oil yields and the formation of high amounts of coke are problems usually encountered
71 when using zeolitic catalysts.

72 Zeolite-based catalysts have been also tested in recent years for the conversion of lignin-
73 rich feedstocks, mainly those derived from the paper production industry. However,
74 lignin catalytic pyrolysis requires typically more severe reaction conditions (higher
75 temperatures and catalyst/feedstock ratios) due to its larger stability and chemical
76 complexity compared to cellulose and hemicellulose [21,22]. Thus, it has been observed
77 that the production of aromatic compounds rises with the temperature, from 500 to 800
78 °C, during lignin catalytic pyrolysis over hierarchical ZSM-5 metal modified (Ga, Zn)
79 zeolites [23]. Likewise, increasing yields of aromatic hydrocarbons and phenolic
80 compounds have been reported when working with catalyst/lignin ratios (C/L) of at least
81 1:1, realising how challenging results the catalytic fragmentation of heavy oligomers
82 derived from lignin thermal decomposition. In this way, Wang et al. [24] obtained at 600
83 °C mass yields of aromatics from the catalytic fast pyrolysis of kraft lignin of 2 – 3 wt.%
84 with C/L ratios in the range 3 - 5 over ZSM-5 derived catalysts. Moreover, Kim et al.
85 reported the increase in the aromatic hydrocarbons production with the temperature,
86 ZSM-5 acidity and catalyst loading, reaching a maximum yield of 3.6 wt.% at 600 °C and
87 C/L 2:1 [25].

88 In contrast, the use of metal oxides (e.g. ZrO₂) has been rarely explored for the catalytic
89 fast pyrolysis (CFP) of lignin. Zheng et al. [26] investigated the effect of different single
90 metal oxides (ZrO₂, TiO₂, WO₃, etc.) or mixed metal oxides nanocomposites on the CFP
91 of organosolv lignin at 600 °C and C/L 10:1. The use of single ZrO₂ did not lead to any
92 aromatic hydrocarbons, while ZrO₂-TiO₂ and WO₃-TiO₂-Al₂O₃ mixed nanocomposites
93 were able to produce aromatics, 3 and 8.5 mol% carbon yield, respectively; being the
94 latter similar to that obtained with HZSM-5 zeolite. These aromatics were obtained by
95 selective cleavage of the C-O bonds within lignin-derived phenols to form aromatics by
96 direct demethoxylation and subsequent dehydration. On the other hand, Elfadly et al.
97 investigated the effect of incorporating ZrO₂ over the material MCM-48 that provided it
98 with new Lewis acidity that improved the BTX production from 17 to 49.4 area%,
99 respectively, at 600 °C and C/L 2:1 [27].

100 Catalyst deactivation effects due to the deposition of large amounts of carbonaceous
101 residues is an important hindrance in lignocellulose catalytic pyrolysis, being even more

102 pronounced when using lignin-rich feedstocks due to the increased production of
103 polyaromatic hydrocarbons, lignin oligomers and other heavy species.

104 In recent years, our research group has been working on the development of zeolite-based
105 catalysts with improved properties for the catalytic pyrolysis and bio-oil upgrading of
106 lignocellulosic feedstocks. In this way, it was recently shown that the incorporation of
107 ZrO_2 to nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite afforded efficient deoxygenation of the bio-oil
108 produced from wheat straw pyrolysis [28] due to an appropriate combination of
109 accessibility and acidic properties. In contrast, there are very few works in the recent
110 literature exploring the incorporation of Zr over ZSM-5, in which the deoxygenation
111 capacity of the catalytic systems or the bio-oil energy yields were not investigated [29,30].
112 In these works, Li et al. reported an improved production of aromatics caused by the
113 progressive increase of the Zr loading over ZSM-5.

114 Besides, we have also investigated the agglomeration of this catalytic system (ZrO_2 /ZSM-
115 5) with attapulgite that contributed to further enhance the bio-oil deoxygenation activity
116 [31]. In the present work, the performance of this material has been investigated in the
117 catalytic pyrolysis of a lignin-rich feedstock. The latter has been obtained after successive
118 fractionation treatments of a lignocellulosic residue to facilitate bioethanol production by
119 fermentation of the extractives. Therefore, the application of catalytic pyrolysis to the
120 remaining solid is expected to increase the overall utilisation of the raw biomass. Catalytic
121 pyrolysis tests have been conducted in an ex-situ system, affording to operate with
122 different temperature values for the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis steps. Thereby,
123 working at relatively low temperature in the catalytic zone allows the production of
124 phenolic compounds to be maximized. These can be more valuable compounds (due to
125 their applications in the production of chemicals) than the aromatic hydrocarbons that
126 would be produced at higher temperatures as reported in the literature with different
127 materials [24–27].

128 The different products obtained have been characterised in detail to obtain a complete
129 view of the process, including an estimation of the contribution of the bio-oil
130 deoxygenation routes. Likewise, from calibrated GC-MS analyses, it has been possible
131 to determine the share of oligomers/heavy species in the bio-oil fraction, concluding that
132 it is sharply decreased when using the ZrO_2 /ZSM-5 technical catalyst. However, previous
133 literature works deal mainly with the quantification and characterisation of the bio-oil

134 components that can be detected by GC-MS, whereas almost no information is provided
135 on the content of oligomers/heavy species [32–36].

136 **2. Experimental**

137 **2.1 Catalyst preparation**

138 The technical catalyst employed consisted of a commercial nanocrystalline ZSM-5 (n-
139 ZSM-5, from CLARIANT, ref. HCZP90, Si/Al = 42), incorporating ZrO₂ over the
140 external surface and agglomerated with attapulgite (ATP), being denoted as ZrO₂/n-ZSM-
141 5-ATP. This material has been prepared in the form of cylinders with 3-4 mm length
142 according to the procedure earlier reported [28,31]. In addition, the parent zeolite (n-
143 ZSM-5) was also used as reference material in the catalytic pyrolysis tests. Both catalysts
144 were employed with the same particle size range (0.18-0.25 mm), for which it was
145 necessary the pelletisation of the nanocrystalline zeolite and the further crushing and
146 sieving of both catalysts.

147 **2.2 Catalyst characterisation**

148 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the catalyst samples were collected with a Philips
149 PW 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD diffractometer using Cu K α radiation (λ = 1.5406 Å),
150 operated at 45 kV and 40 mA. The catalyst composition (Al and Zr contents) was obtained
151 by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) using a Perkin
152 Elmer Optima 7300 AD instrument after the digestion of the samples with an HF/HNO₃
153 solution in a microwave oven (Anton PaarMW3000).

154 The textural properties of the catalysts were measured by argon adsorption-desorption
155 isotherms at -186 °C in an AUTOSORB iQ Analyzer System (Quantachrome
156 Instruments), previously degassed at 300 °C for 3 h. BET surface was determined by the
157 Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) equation in the range of P/P₀= 0.05–0.15. The
158 contribution of both micro- and mesopores to the textural properties was calculated
159 applying the NL-DFT (non-local density functional theory) model to the adsorption
160 branch of the isotherm, assuming cylindrical pore geometry.

161 **2.3 Lignin-rich residue**

162 The lignin-rich feedstock was obtained from a lignocellulosic residue, proceeding from
163 the pruning and cleaning of gardens, which was subjected to three consecutive processes
164 for the extraction of the holocellulose biopolymers. Thereby, the gardening residue was
165 initially milled in a laboratory cutting mill (SM 2000, Retsch, Germany) with a sieve of
166 10 mm to obtain milled gardening chips. Then, the fractionation scheme included: i)
167 aqueous extraction, ii) acid-catalysed steam explosion, and iii) enzymatic hydrolysis. The
168 details of the experimental procedures have been provided elsewhere [37]. The first stage
169 (aqueous extraction) was aimed to hydrolyse and recover the non-structural components,
170 while the major goal of the second stage (acid-catalysed steam explosion) was to generate
171 a cellulose-enriched solid fraction, which was used finally for glucose production by
172 enzymatic hydrolysis in the third stage. The slurry so obtained was vacuum filtered to
173 separate the liquid and solid fractions. The latter (lignin-rich residue) was frozen and dried
174 by lyophilisation, being then used as feedstock for the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis
175 experiments.

176 **2.4 Pyrolysis tests**

177 The pyrolysis tests of the lignin-rich residue were performed in a lab-scale fixed-bed
178 reactor (Fig. 1), whose technical specifications have been detailed in a previous work
179 [38]. They were carried out under atmospheric pressure and at temperatures between 500
180 and 650 °C (for the thermal zone), and 450 °C (for the catalytic zone). Firstly, about 4 g
181 of the lignin residue (previously dried at 105 °C overnight) were loaded in the biomass
182 tank. Before each experiment, the setup was purged with N₂ until reaching O₂
183 concentration levels in the exiting gases below 0.1 vol.%, to ensure an inert atmosphere.
184 Once the system was purged and the setpoint temperature was reached, the feeding valve
185 was opened provoking the falling of the lignin-rich biomass into the reactor. In this way,
186 this material was rapidly heated and thermally decomposed, releasing the volatile matter
187 and forming a solid residue (char), which is accumulated in the thermal zone. The volatile
188 matter is pushed down by a 100 mL/min N₂ flow, passing through the catalyst bed (in the
189 case of the catalytic tests) and leaving the reactor towards the condensation system.
190 Finally, the bio-oil fraction is collected in the condensation system composed by four
191 flasks connected in series, which has been partially modified regarding that used in
192 previous works due to the nature of the lignin-rich feedstock that provokes the presence
193 of high content of heavy compounds, mainly phenolics, in the bio-oil. Accordingly, the
194 first flask is kept at 70 °C by a hot water bath to avoid that heavy compounds can be

195 solidified, blocking the flask tubes, while the subsequent three flasks were maintained at
196 0 °C with a water-ice bath, in which most of the lighter bio-oil compounds are condensed
197 in the first of them. Finally, non-condensable gases are collected in a sampling bag for
198 further analysis by GC.

199 Catalytic pyrolysis tests were carried out in the same way, establishing in the catalyst bed
200 a temperature of 450 °C and operating with values of the catalyst to biomass (lignin-rich
201 residue) ratio (C/B) between 0.2 and 0.8 g/g by increasing the amount of catalyst placed
202 in the catalyst bed from 0.8 to 3.2 g, while lignin-rich residue amount is kept constant at
203 4 g for the catalytic tests.

204

205 Fig. 1. Lab-scale set up for the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis tests, provided with a
206 condensation system adapted for collecting bio-oils rich in heavy compounds coming
207 from lignin decomposition.

208 2.5 Characterisation of both lignin-rich feedstock and pyrolysis products

209 2.5.1. Proximate and elemental analysis

210 Proximate analysis of lignin and chars were performed according to European standards.
211 Thus, moisture content (UNE-EN ISO 18134-1:2016) was obtained by heating the sample
212 in an oven at 105 °C, which was kept overnight. Volatile matter content (UNE-EN ISO
213 18123:2016) was assessed by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in a thermobalance

214 NETZSCH STA 449 heating up the sample to 900 °C at 10 °C/min and maintaining this
215 temperature for 10 min. Ash content (UNE-EN ISO 18122:2016) was determined in a
216 muffle furnace at 900 °C for 1 h in air atmosphere. Fixed carbon was calculated by
217 difference. The chemical composition of lignin ash was determined by ICP-OES.
218 Elemental analysis of lignin residue and pyrolysis products (char, bio-oil and coke) were
219 performed in a Thermo Scientific micro-elemental analyser, where C, H, N, S contents
220 were directly obtained, while that of O was calculated by difference. Lastly, the amount
221 of coke deposited over the catalyst surface was measured by TGA analysis, in which the
222 spent catalyst was exposed to a heating program from room temperature up to 900 °C at
223 10 °C/min in an air atmosphere. Thus, the amount of coke was determined as the weight
224 loss of the spent catalyst and its composition was assessed from the elemental analysis
225 (C, H, N, S and O by difference) of the spent catalyst.

226 2.5.2. Gas chromatography

227 Gas chromatography was used to determine the composition of the gaseous fraction,
228 which was formed by CO, CO₂, H₂ and light hydrocarbons (CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, C₃H₈,
229 C₄H₈ y C₄H₁₀). This analysis was carried out using a dual channel Agilent CP-4900
230 Micro-GC, equipped with two different columns, a CP-MolSieve 5Å of 10 m length and
231 a P-PoraPLOT Q of 10 m length, with He as the carrier gas.

232 2.5.3 Karl-Fischer titration

233 The water content (in wt.%) of the bio-oil fraction was determined with a Mettler-Toledo
234 V20S compact volumetric Karl–Fischer titrator.

235 2.5.4 Gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

236 Molecular composition of the organic fraction in bio-oil (bio-oil*, i.e. on water-free basis)
237 was analysed by GC-MS using a Bruker® SCION 436-GC, provided with a fused silica
238 column (30 m × 0.25 mm ID × 0.25 μm), with He as carrier gas (1 mL/min). Compound
239 identification was performed by means of the NIST EI-MS v 2.0 spectral library, with a
240 minimum match of 700. The identified compounds were classified according to their
241 main functional group: short-chain carboxylic acids (AC), light oxygenates (LO), furans
242 (FUR), oxygenated aromatics (OAR), aromatic hydrocarbons (AR) and sugars (SUG).
243 Moreover, the group of oxygenated aromatics was divided into alkylphenols (PHE),
244 guaiacols (GUA), syringols (SYR), catechols (CAT) and methoxybenzenes (METH).

245 External calibration of the main compounds of each family was carried out in order to
246 calculate their respective mass concentrations.

247 **2.6 Mass and energy yields**

248 The mass yield (Y_{wi}) of the different pyrolysis products/fractions was calculated, referred
249 to the weight of the raw feedstock (m_f), according to the following equation:

$$250 \quad Y_{wi} (\text{wt. } \%) = (m_i/m_f) * 100 \quad (1)$$

251 Where m_i represents the corresponding product or fraction weight (char, bio-oil*, water,
252 gas and coke). All tests were validated with a mass balance closure of 100 ± 5 wt.%.

253 In a similar way, the energy yield (Y_{Ei}) of products/fractions was calculated by the
254 following equation:

$$255 \quad Y_{Ei} (\%) = (HHV_i m_i / HHV_f m_f) * 100 \quad (2)$$

256 The high heating value (HHV) was calculated using the equation proposed by Channiwala
257 and Parikh [39], from the elemental analysis of the lignin-rich residue and pyrolysis
258 products, which is valid for a wide range of compositions of solid, liquid and gaseous
259 fuels.

260 The overall deoxygenation selectivity (ODS) corresponding to the different routes
261 (dehydration, decarbonylation and decarboxylation) was calculated according to
262 Equation 3:

$$263 \quad ODS (\%) = 100 * (O_k / \Sigma O_k) \quad (3)$$

264 Where, O_k represents the oxygen contained in the produced H_2O , CO or CO_2 . Moreover,
265 the catalytic deoxygenation selectivity (CDS) was determined in a similar way taking into
266 account the incremental production of H_2O , CO and CO_2 in the catalytic tests subtracting
267 that corresponding to the thermal pyrolysis experiment.

268 The concentration of any of the components detected by GC-MS in the bio-oil* (C_i) was
269 calculated from the division of its mass yield by the bio-oil* overall mass yield. Finally,
270 the fraction of the total bio-oil* mass yield detected by GC-MS was estimated from the
271 sum of all the detected components with respect to the overall bio-oil* mass yield.

272 **3. Results and discussion**

273 **3.1. Properties of the lignin-rich feedstock**

274 The lignin-rich feedstock used in this work proceeds from a lignocellulosic residue of
275 pruning and cleaning of gardens, which was subjected to three consecutive processes for
276 the extraction of a great part of the holocellulose components. The initial biomass
277 contained 24.8, 15.7 and 21.6 wt.% of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, respectively,
278 in addition to extractives (18.2 wt.%), proteins (7.2 wt.%), acetyl groups (2.1 wt.%), ash
279 (7.2 wt.%) and other compounds (3.2 wt.%). After the extraction process, the recovered
280 solid represented 38 wt.% of the raw biomass, being composed of 18.5, 4.3 and 67.2 wt.%
281 of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, respectively. The remaining matter corresponds to
282 other compounds (4.6 wt.%) and ash (5.4 wt.%). This material was sieved to homogenize
283 its particle size to 0.5-1 mm.

284 Figure S1 displays the thermal behaviour (TGA analyses) of both the raw lignocellulose
285 and the lignin-rich residue under an inert atmosphere. The DTG curve of the raw
286 lignocellulose has been deconvoluted into three main peaks that can be assigned to the
287 three biopolymers: hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin with peak maxima at 282 °C, 323
288 °C and 348 °C, respectively. Nevertheless, the extractives and proteins present in
289 significant amounts in this material may also contribute to the DTG signals, overlapping
290 with those of the biopolymers. Thus, it has been reported that the thermal decomposition
291 of extractives takes place in the same temperature range as that of hemicellulose [40],
292 whereas proteins undergo thermal fragmentation in a wide temperature range with peak
293 maximum just above 300 °C [41], i.e. very close to that of cellulose. On the other hand,
294 the DTG curve of the lignin-rich residue can be deconvoluted into two main peaks with
295 shares of 21.4 and 78.6 %, respectively. The narrow peak at 331 °C can be assigned
296 mainly to the cellulose thermal decomposition, whereas the broad signal with a maximum
297 at 314 °C is coming mainly from lignin with minor contributions of the hemicellulose and
298 other components still present in this sample. Moreover, this peak is somewhat shifted
299 towards lower temperatures (314 °C versus 348 °C) in comparison to the raw
300 lignocellulose, suggesting that the lignin undergo partial depolymerisation during the
301 holocellulose extractive treatments. The char finally obtained in the TGA experiments
302 represents 26.4 wt.% and 31.8 wt.% of the raw lignocellulose and lignin-rich materials,
303 respectively. These values are consistent with the well-known higher tendency of lignin
304 for the formation of char in comparison with holocellulose biopolymers.

305 Table 1 summarises the proximate and elemental analysis of the raw lignocellulosic
 306 biomass and those of the lignin-rich residue. After the holocellulose extraction processes,
 307 the volatile matter decreased from 82.5 to 74.5 wt.%; while the fixed carbon increased
 308 from 14.2 to 22.4 wt.% as a consequence of the partial removal of cellulose and
 309 hemicellulose. The same trend is observed for the carbon content, whereas a significant
 310 decrease is observed for that of oxygen (from 42.4 wt.% to 34.4 wt.%). These changes
 311 are in agreement with the biopolymer share in both materials since the oxygen content of
 312 cellulose (49 wt.%) and hemicellulose (53 wt.%) is quite higher than that of lignin (21 –
 313 30 wt.%). On the other hand, the elemental composition of the lignin-rich sample fits well
 314 with the values reported in the literature for solid residues obtained by combining steam
 315 explosion and enzymatic hydrolysis (C = 53 - 65 wt.%, H = 5.5 - 6.4 wt.%, N = 1 - 3
 316 wt.%, and O = 28 - 39 wt.%) [42]. The HHV of the lignin-rich feedstock is higher than
 317 that of the raw lignocellulose, but still significantly lower than those of conventional fossil
 318 fuels (e.g. crude oil, 42-47 MJ/kg) due to its high oxygen content.

319 Table 1. Proximate and elemental analyses of the initial biomass and the lignin-rich
 320 residue.

	Lignocellulosic biomass	Lignin-rich residue
Moisture (wt.%)	1.2	5.5
Proximate analysis (wt.%, db [*])		
Volatile matter	82.5	74.5
Ash	3.3	3.1
Fixed carbon	14.2	22.4
Elemental analysis (wt.%, daf ^{**})		
C	50.1	56.8
H	6.1	6.4
N	1.5	2.4
O	42.4	34.4
HHV (MJ/kg)	19.5	23.0

321
 322

* db: dry basis

** daf: dry and ash-free basis

323 **3.2 Catalyst properties**

324 The technical catalyst employed in this work consists of a nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite,
 325 modified by impregnation with ZrO₂ and agglomerated with attapulgite. A summary of

326 the properties of this material in comparison with those of the parent zeolite is next
327 provided.

328 XRD patterns of n-ZSM-5 and ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP catalysts, shown in Fig. S1A, present
329 the typical diffraction peaks of the MFI zeolitic structure, although with a significant
330 shielding effect in the case of the technical catalyst arising from the clay binder [31].
331 Moreover, no diffractions peaks of crystalline ZrO₂ are observed due to its high dispersion
332 over the external surface of the nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite, as it was reported in
333 previous studies [28,31]. Textural properties, determined from the Ar adsorption-
334 desorption isotherms, are summarised in Table S1. The technical catalyst has lower values
335 for all the textural properties than the parent n-ZSM-5, due mainly to the presence of
336 attapulgite as this clay exhibits quite lower surface area and porosity than the zeolite.
337 Nevertheless, the interesting fact is that both catalysts show high values of the
338 mesopore/external surface, which is an important aspect to favour the conversion of bulky
339 molecules like those present in the bio-oil produced by lignin pyrolysis. The acid and
340 basic properties of the catalysts were probed by NH₃ and CO₂ temperature-programmed
341 desorption (TPDs), respectively (Table S1).

342 The incorporation of ZrO₂ into n-ZSM-5 results in the generation of new types of acidic
343 sites of different strength, while creating a certain amount of basicity, thanks to the
344 amphoteric properties of zirconia [43]. After the agglomeration with attapulgite
345 additional acid and basic centres appear due to a partial migration of Mg²⁺ cations from
346 the clay to the zeolite and their interactions with the ZrO₂ nanoparticles [31]. Therefore,
347 these synergies between their components conferred the final technical catalyst with
348 interesting multi-functional acid-basic properties. Additional characterisation details of
349 the technical catalyst can be found elsewhere [44].

350 **3.3 Thermal pyrolysis tests**

351 In comparison with lignocellulose feedstocks, the thermal decomposition of lignin-rich
352 residues is more greatly affected by temperature, since lignin fragmentation occurs in a
353 broader range of temperatures (200 – 600 °C) than cellulose (300 – 375 °C) and
354 hemicellulose (200 – 300 °C). Thereby, the effect of the pyrolysis temperature was
355 initially studied in this work within the range 500 – 650 °C. Thermal experiments were
356 denoted as TP (thermal pyrolysis) followed by the value of the temperature in the two
357 zones (upper and down) of the reactor (e.g. TP 600/450). Fig. 2A shows the effect of the

358 pyrolysis temperature on the mass yield of the different fractions. It can be observed that
 359 char yield progressively decreased with temperature (from 33 to 25 wt.%) getting closer
 360 to the fixed carbon content of the feedstock (22 wt.%), which is accompanied by an
 361 increase in the production of volatiles (gases and bio-oil). The effect of the
 362 devolatilisation phenomena can be further appreciated in the proximate and elemental
 363 analysis of the char samples, which are collected in Table S2. The rise in the pyrolysis
 364 temperature favours the loss of volatile matter with a high H/C ratio and therefore, this
 365 devolatilisation together with charring reactions give rise to a more condensed and with
 366 higher carbon content char structures [45]. These variations are reflected in the increase
 367 of the carbon content (from 80.6 to 87.8 wt.%) and the reduction of the oxygen
 368 concentration (from 13.6 to 7.4 wt.%) of the char with the temperature increase, which
 369 results in an enhancement of the HHV (up to 28.1 MJ/kg) compared to that of the starting
 370 lignin-rich residue (23.9 MJ/kg). The ash content of the char increases progressively with
 371 the pyrolysis temperature, which denotes that the inorganic matter present in the feedstock
 372 remains mainly in the carbonaceous residue. Thus, the ash yield in the pyrolysis tests
 373 matches quite well with the ash contained in the raw lignin-rich residue.

375 Fig. 2. Mass yields (Y_{w_i}) of pyrolysis products (A) and components of the gaseous
 376 fraction (B) in the thermal pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue.
 377 GO: gaseous olefins (C_2-C_4), GP: gaseous paraffins (C_2-C_4).

378 Regarding the gas fraction, an upward trend is observed with the temperature (from 9.5
 379 to 13.9 wt.%) in the yield of all the components, as shown in Fig. 2B. Thus, the CO yield
 380 increases progressively up to 650 °C, while the CO₂ concentration follows this same trend
 381 up to 600 °C, temperature from which it no longer increases. On the other hand, the yield
 382 of light hydrocarbons rises with the temperature because of the extension of severe
 383 cracking reactions. This effect is more pronounced in the case of light olefins in

384 comparison with gaseous paraffins, which can be connected with the enhancement in the
385 hydrogen yield with the temperature, showing the occurrence of dehydrogenation
386 reactions.

387 In line with the other fractions, the bio-oil* yield is also influenced by temperature,
388 increasing slightly up to 600 °C (from 49.5 to 53.7 wt.%), from which it is reduced as a
389 result of the cracking of organic species to give gaseous components. On the other hand,
390 the yield of water practically remains stable in the range 500 - 600 °C (from 7.9 to 8.3
391 wt.%), being increased up to 11.4 wt.% when working at 650 °C. Table 2 shows the bio-
392 oil* elemental analysis as a function of the pyrolysis temperature. The carbon content of
393 bio-oil* samples increases with temperature, while that of oxygen is reduced. These
394 changes in the bio-oil* composition provoke a slight increase in its HHV with the
395 pyrolysis temperature.

396 Table 2. Elemental analysis and HHV of the bio-oil* produced by thermal pyrolysis of
397 the lignin-rich residue at different temperatures.

Experiment	Bio-oil* elemental analysis (wt.%)				HHV (MJ/kg _{bio-oil*})
	C	H	N	O	
TP 500/450	56.3	26.2	3.3	32.0	26.2
TP 550/450	58.1	26.8	3.2	30.4	26.8
TP 600/450	58.5	26.9	3.4	30.0	26.9
TP 650/450	60.8	28.0	3.7	27.3	28.0

398 Fig. 3A depicts the overall selectivity towards the different deoxygenation routes
399 (dehydration, decarbonylation and decarboxylation), calculated from the H₂O, CO and
400 CO₂ yields. Dehydration is the predominant pathway with selectivity in the 50 – 56%
401 range, followed by decarboxylation (30 – 36%), and finally decarbonylation (10 – 14%).
402 These results are qualitatively in agreement with those obtained with different
403 lignocelluloses (forestry and agricultural residues), although the latter presented a larger
404 share of dehydration (68 – 75%), and lower contribution of decarboxylation (18 – 24%)
405 and decarbonylation (6 – 8%) [46].

406
 407 Fig. 3. Overall deoxygenation selectivities (*ODS*) (A) and energy yield distribution (B)
 408 in the thermal pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue at different temperatures.

409 For the lignin-rich residue, decarbonylation and decarboxylation are slightly favoured
 410 with the increase of the temperature (up to 600 °C in case of CO₂ formation) to the
 411 detriment of water formation. However, at the highest temperature (650 °C),
 412 decarboxylation route declined in favour of dehydration.

413 Fig. 3B plots the effect of temperature on the chemical energy yield of the different
 414 product fractions. It can be observed a reduction in the char energy yield with the increase
 415 of the temperature, despite this solid being progressively enriched in carbon (Table S2),
 416 which in turn increases its HHV. However, this effect does not compensate the loss of
 417 mass yield of this fraction when increasing the pyrolysis temperature. In contrast, a
 418 continuous increment is observed for the chemical energy contained in the gases, coming
 419 from the presence of CO, light hydrocarbons and hydrogen, although in all cases with a
 420 low share (energy yield varying from 3 to 7%). Regarding bio-oil*, an increase in the
 421 energy yield is observed when passing from 500 to 550 °C, remaining then practically
 422 constant up to 650 °C. This effect is due to the fact that, despite the bio-oil* mass
 423 production decreases at 650 °C, its energy yield is compensated by the lower oxygen
 424 content, which in turn is reflected in a higher HHV. Interestingly, the data in this figure
 425 show that about 65% of the chemical energy contained in the raw lignin-rich feedstock is
 426 accumulated in the bio-oil* fraction after the pyrolysis process.

427 GC-MS analyses have been used to determine the molecular composition of the bio-oil*
 428 fraction. Typically, this technique is employed in a semi-quantitative way providing the
 429 results as area% of all detected components [47,48]. However, a great part of bio-oil*
 430 consists of heavy species that cannot be detected nor identified by GC-MS. In this work,
 431 we have used a calibration method that includes the main components of the different

432 families detected by the GC-MS, so their wt.% concentration and yield can be calculated.
 433 Moreover, by difference to the overall bio-oil* yield, it is also possible to estimate the
 434 mass contribution of the heavy species not detected by GC-MS. The results so obtained
 435 for the bio-oils* produced in the thermal pyrolysis tests of the lignin-rich residue are
 436 illustrated in Fig. 4.

437
 438 Fig. 4. Total and GC-MS detected (white striped pattern) mass (A) and energy (B) yields
 439 of the thermal pyrolysis bio-oils*; concentration of main compound families (C) and
 440 concentration of oxygenated aromatics subfamilies (D) in the bio-oils*.

441 According to parts (A) and (B) of Fig. 4, the GC-MS detected components represent just
 442 a small fraction of the whole bio-oil* in terms of both mass (about 16.2 – 18.4%) and
 443 energy (about 16.1 – 17.9%) yield. This share is little changed when varying the pyrolysis
 444 temperature between 500 and 650 °C. In the same way, regarding the raw biomass, the
 445 yield obtained for the GC-MS detected components is just about 8.7 – 9.3% in terms of
 446 mass and slightly higher (10.3 – 10.9%) if expressed in the form of chemical energy.
 447 Therefore, the bio-oil* produced from the lignin-rich residue is formed mostly by heavy
 448 species, coming from the partial decomposition of the biopolymers or through secondary
 449 reactions between primary pyrolysis products, which may strongly limit its valorisation

450 and commercial application. Similar results have been reported when using other
 451 lignocellulosic biomass, such as wheat straw, having a high content of mineral matter that
 452 may be responsible of catalysing oligomer formation and charring reactions [46,49].
 453 Accordingly, this could be also the case in the present work since the raw biomass
 454 employed contains 3.1 wt.% ash.

455 Regarding the bio-oil* components detected by GC-MS, it can be observed in Fig. 4C
 456 and Table 3 that oxygenated aromatics (OAR), short-chain carboxylic acids (AC), and
 457 sugars (SUG) are the main families being detected.

458 Table 3. Concentration of main compounds detected by GC-MS analysis in thermal bio-
 459 oils*.

Family	C_i (wt.%)	TP 500/450	TP 550/450	TP 600/450	TP 650/450
AC	Acetic acid	1.96	1.84	2.19	2.64
	Propanoic acid	0.11	0.21	0.31	0.27
LO	2-Propanone, 1-hydroxy-	0.26	0.26	0.31	0.34
	2-Cyclopenten-1-one	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
FUR	Furfural	0.18	0.17	0.22	0.28
	2(5H)-Furanone	0.19	0.16	0.18	0.25
PHE	Phenol	0.14	0.08	0.17	0.32
	p-cresol	0.18	0.13	0.24	0.34
GUA	Guaiacol	0.46	0.32	0.53	0.58
	Isoeugenol	0.87	0.82	0.78	0.72
O-AR	Creosol	0.46	0.36	0.54	0.59
	Syringol	1.21	1.07	0.97	0.84
SYR	Phenol, 2,6-dimethoxy-4-(2-propenyl)-	1.60	1.48	1.20	1.02
CAT	1,2-Benzenediol, 3-methoxy-	0.32	0.47	0.43	0.40
	Catechol	0.14	0.11	0.15	0.22
METH	1,2,4-Trimethoxybenzene	1.11	1.01	0.87	0.72
SUG	Levoglucosan	2.89	2.95	3.09	3.41
AR	BTX	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Other alkyl benzenes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Alkyl naphthalenes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

460 Variation of the pyrolysis temperature between 500 and 650 °C has just a small effect on
 461 the relative proportion of these families of compounds (see Table 3). In the case of the

462 AC family, acetic acid is by far the major component, being formed by fragmentation of
463 hemicellulose and cellulose-derived products, as well as by cracking of lignin side chains.
464 The presence of sugars in bio-oil*, principally levoglucosan (2.89-4.41 wt.%
465 concentration), is linked to the cellulose remaining in the feedstock, which was not totally
466 extracted during the pre-treatments. Furan compounds (FUR), as well as ketones and
467 ethers (KET & ETH), are also detected by GC-MS although in low concentrations and
468 yields. On the other hand, the absence of aromatic hydrocarbons is remarkable, indicating
469 that they are not produced during thermal degradation despite the significant
470 concentration of OAR compounds in the bio-oil*, denoting that the latter are hardly
471 deoxygenated in the absence of catalyst.

472 Fig. 4D displays the OAR lump of compounds divided into different subfamilies:
473 guaiacols (GUA), syringols (SYR), phenolics (PHE), methoxybenzenes (METH) and
474 catechols (CAT). GUA and SYR are the most abundant compounds within the OAR
475 family. Some influence of the temperature can be denoted in terms of these subfamilies,
476 with the yields of phenolics, guaiacols and catechols increasing with the temperature,
477 while those of syringols and methoxybenzenes being lowered. This can be explained by
478 the breakage of the methoxy and methyl groups at high temperatures. Thus, syringol can
479 be transformed into guaiacol and 3-methyl-catechol through demethoxylation and
480 demethylation pathways, respectively.

481 **3.4 Catalytic pyrolysis tests**

482 Once the temperature of the thermal pyrolysis was established at 600 °C, the catalytic
483 upgrading of the thermal pyrolysis vapours was investigated with the technical catalyst
484 $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{n-ZSM-5-ATP}$. In particular, it was studied the effect of increasing values of
485 catalyst to biomass (lignin-rich residue) ratio (C/B), 0.2, 0.4 and 0.8 g/g, on the mass and
486 energy yields, and the elemental and molecular composition of bio-oil*. Moreover, the
487 performance of the parent n-ZSM-5 sample was studied at C/B = 0.2 g/g to be used as
488 reference. Experiments were named as CP (catalytic pyrolysis), followed by ZC (zeolite
489 catalyst) or TZC (technical zeolite catalyst) depending on whether the catalyst used was
490 n-ZSM-5 or $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{n-ZSM-5-ATP}$, respectively, and indicating as well the
491 catalysts/biomass ratio (C/B), e.g.: CP-TZC (C/B=0.2).

492 Fig. 5 displays the results obtained when varying the C/B ratio with the technical catalyst
493 on the yields of the different fractions (A), and the gaseous components (B).

494

495 Fig. 5. Mass yields (Y_{w_i}) of the different fractions (A) and of gaseous components (B) in
 496 the catalytic pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue. GO: gaseous olefins (C₂-C₄), GP gaseous
 497 paraffins (C₂-C₄).

498 As expected, the production and elemental composition (Table S2) of the char remained
 499 almost the same in all experiments since this product is formed in the upper part of the
 500 reactor, and it does not enter into contact with the catalyst bed. Compared to the thermal
 501 test, a second carbonaceous residue (coke) is generated and deposited over the catalysts.
 502 In the case of the ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP sample the coke mass yield increased significantly
 503 with the C/B ratio (from 2.4 to 8.0 wt.%). However, in terms of coke content in the
 504 catalyst, the variation is less pronounced, being slightly reduced (from 11.6 to 9.9 wt.%)
 505 with the increase of the C/B ratio as recorded in Table 4. Moreover, a trend to increase
 506 the carbon content of coke, while reducing the oxygen one, is observed in Table 4 with
 507 the rise of the C/B ratio, denoting a variation in the nature of these carbonaceous residues
 508 along the catalyst bed from high to low oxygenated species. Coke formation over both
 509 catalysts (ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP and n-ZSM-5), at the same catalyst loading (C/B = 0.2),
 510 takes place with similar mass yields (2.4 and 2.3 wt.% respectively). Nevertheless, there
 511 was a noteworthy difference between them in terms of elemental composition. Thus, the
 512 carbon content is higher for n-ZSM-5 (78.0 wt.%) compared to the technical catalyst (66.0
 513 wt.%), whereas the opposite is observed for the oxygen content (10.4 and 25.9 wt.%,
 514 respectively). This effect was similar to that previously observed when using
 515 lignocellulose as feedstock [38,44]. The lower carbonisation degree of the coke formed
 516 over the technical catalyst can be assigned to the incorporation of both ZrO₂ and
 517 attapulgite, which moderates the strong acidity present in the parent zeolite [31], thus
 518 attenuating the evolution of the these carbonaceous deposits through aromatisation and
 519 ring condensation reactions.

520 Table 4. Elemental analysis and HHV of the coke fraction formed during catalytic
 521 pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue.

Experiment	Coke in catalyst (wt.%)	Coke elemental analysis (wt.%)				HHV (MJ/kg _{coke})
		C	H	N	O	
CP-ZC (C/B=0.2)	11.3	78.0	6.0	5.5	10.4	33.2
CP-TZC (C/B=0.2)	11.6	66.0	5.7	2.4	25.9	27.0
CP-TZC (C/B=0.4)	10.3	69.6	6.9	0.1	23.4	30.0
CP-TZC (C/B=0.8)	9.9	72.8	6.8	1.5	18.9	31.4

522 Regarding the gaseous fraction, the addition of a catalyst and the increment of the catalyst
 523 load lead to a significant increase of the gas yield (growing from 12.5 to 21.5 wt.%). As
 524 it can be observed in Fig. 5B, CO and CO₂ are the predominant components in the gases
 525 as it occurred in the thermal experiments, showing that the technical catalyst promotes
 526 extensively decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions. While the yield
 527 corresponding to methane and gaseous paraffins (GP) increase just slightly with the C/B
 528 ratio, the production of gaseous olefins (GO) is strongly enhanced, especially for the
 529 highest catalyst load (C/B = 0.8 g/g). This fact can be related to a number of reactions
 530 that are favoured by the zeolite-based catalyst, such as deoxygenation and cracking of
 531 light oxygenates derived from the decomposition of the holocellulose biopolymers still
 532 present in the feedstock and dealkylation reactions of the lignin-derived fragments [38].
 533 Comparing the performance of both catalysts at C/B = 0.2, just minor differences are
 534 observed between them. The parent n-ZSM-5 produced a lower total amount of gases
 535 compared to ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP, due to the reduction of CO and CO₂ yields, in spite of
 536 the larger formation of GO, GP and H₂. This finding evidences that the technical catalyst
 537 promotes in higher extension than the parent one deoxygenation reactions by
 538 decarbonylation / decarboxylation pathways, while leading to less severe cracking, which
 539 can be assigned to the adjustment of their acid-base properties achieved by the
 540 incorporation of both ZrO₂ and attapulgite to the parent zeolite [31].

541 The liquid fraction suffered significant changes with the addition of catalyst and the
 542 variation of the C/B ratio. Water yield increased strongly in the presence of the catalysts
 543 and slightly with the catalyst load. Thus, the production of water increases from 8.4 to
 544 15.9 wt.%, when comparing the thermal pyrolysis test and the catalytic one using ZrO₂/n-

545 ZSM-5-ATP at C/B = 0.2 g/g. Water is mainly released from dehydration and
 546 condensation reactions, which are promoted by the zeolite-based catalysts. Once the so
 547 involved functional groups are consumed at high C/B ratios, the water production is
 548 levelled-off [38]. On the other hand, the yield of the organic liquid components (bio-oil*)
 549 decreased greatly with the catalyst loading, due to the occurrence of deoxygenation,
 550 cracking and coking reactions of the pyrolysis vapours promoted by the technical catalyst.
 551 The significant increment in the water formation and the changes experienced in the
 552 elemental composition of bio-oil*, with a decrease in the oxygen content as indicated
 553 below, caused the separation of the liquid fraction in two phases for all the catalytic
 554 experiments. The aqueous phase contains most of the water and hydrophilic compounds,
 555 such as acids and light oxygenates. In contrast, the organic phase presents little water (9
 556 – 15 wt.%), being formed mainly by relatively hydrophobic compounds. Comparing bio-
 557 oil* yields obtained with n-ZSM-5 and ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP catalysts, a slightly superior
 558 yield is produced with the parent zeolite, which agrees well with its lower deoxygenation
 559 activity as corroborated by the lower water, CO and CO₂ formation over this material.

560 The decrease of the bio-oil* yield is, in a great part, a consequence of the upgrading
 561 process provoked by the catalyst activity, mainly by reducing its oxygen content. Thus,
 562 important changes are appreciated in the bio-oil* elemental composition as summarised
 563 in Table 5.

564 Table 5. Elemental composition, water content and HHV of the bio-oil fraction obtained
 565 in the catalytic pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue.

Experiment	Bio-oil H ₂ O content (wt.%)	Bio-oil* elemental analysis (wt.%)				HHV (MJ/kg _{bio-oil*})
		C	H	N	O	
TP 600/450	13.4	58.4	8.2	3.4	30.0	26.9
CP-ZC (C/B=0.2)	27.1	65.5	7.9	4.1	22.5	29.8
CP-TZC (C/B=0.2)	28.6	70.3	8.5	4.0	19.2	32.5
CP-TZC (C/B=0.4)	34.3	71.4	8.5	5.2	14.9	33.3
CP-TZC (C/B=0.8)	40.0	74.6	8.7	6.3	10.4	35.1

566 It can be observed a pronounced decrease in the oxygen content, from 30.0 to 10.4 wt.%
 567 at the highest catalyst load, leading to an increase in the carbon concentration (from 58.4
 568 to 74.6 wt.%), while the hydrogen content is little affected. As a result, the value of the

569 bio-oil* HHV is enhanced significantly, passing from 26.9 MJ/kg for the thermal
 570 pyrolysis test up to 35.1 MJ/kg in the case of the experiment performed over the technical
 571 catalyst with the highest C/B ratio. The oxygen content of the bio-oil* produced with the
 572 parent n-ZSM-5 decreased as well, but not at the same extent as with ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP
 573 catalyst, proving that this last catalyst had an enhanced deoxygenation activity due to the
 574 beneficial effects caused by the zeolite modification with zirconia and attapulgite.

575 The changes of the bio-oil* composition can be clearly seen on the van Krevelen graph
 576 of Fig. 6, which represents the effective H/C ratio versus the O/C one. The former has
 577 been calculated as $H_{\text{eff}}/C=(H-2O-3N-2S)/C$ to account only for the hydrogen that could
 578 be finally available if all the oxygen present in the bio-oil is removed in the form of water
 579 [50,51].

580
 581 Fig. 6. Van Krevelen graphs of the raw biomass, the lignin-rich residue and both thermal
 582 and catalytic bio-oils*.

583 The raw lignin-rich residue presents a position in this graph more favourable than the raw
 584 lignocellulose, regarding its possible transformation into advanced biofuels with a
 585 composition closer to that of fossil fuels. This fact is a consequence of the pre-treatments
 586 applied to the raw biomass to remove a great part of holocellulose, thus reducing the
 587 oxygen content while increasing the hydrogen concentration. Likewise, the thermal

588 pyrolysis of the residue has a positive effect as it produces a bio-oil* fraction with lower
589 oxygen and increasing the H_{eff}/C up to around 0.8. However, variation of the temperature
590 in the thermal pyrolysis tests has a small effect, with some decrease of the O/C ratio but
591 keeping almost constant the H_{eff}/C values. A quite similar effect is produced by the n-
592 ZSM-5 catalyst, as it affords further bio-oil* deoxygenation but without improving the
593 H_{eff}/C ratio. In contrast, the technical catalyst provokes positive changes regarding both
594 parameters. Thus, the O/C ratio is reduced and the H_{eff}/C is enhanced with the increase
595 of the catalyst loading, approaching the region corresponding to fossil fuels in the van
596 Krevelen graph.

597 The deoxygenation selectivities corresponding to the catalytic step are illustrated in Fig.
598 7A. These values have been calculated from the incremental yield of water, CO and CO₂
599 produced in the catalytic tests regarding the thermal pyrolysis experiment. Dehydration
600 is in all cases the major deoxygenation pathway, showing selectivities even higher than
601 those of the thermal pyrolysis tests, earlier illustrated in Fig. 3A. Thus, when using the
602 parent n-ZSM-5, the catalytic dehydration selectivity is over 90%, i.e. most of the
603 deoxygenation activity with this material is associated to the release of water, whereas it
604 does not show any decarboxylation activity. On the other hand, for the technical catalyst,
605 the dehydration selectivity is somewhat lower than for the n-ZSM-5, being progressively
606 reduced with the rise in the catalyst loading as it favours the extension of decarboxylation
607 and decarbonylation routes. However, dehydration is still by far the main deoxygenation
608 pathway at any C/B ratio. This behaviour is significantly different from that previously
609 reported when using this technical catalyst with wheat straw as feedstock [44]. In this
610 case, the relative contribution of the three catalytic deoxygenation pathways was more
611 balanced. Moreover, decarbonylation became in this case the major deoxygenation route
612 at high C/B ratios. These results denote that the catalytic deoxygenation selectivity of the
613 technical catalyst is largely influenced by the feedstock composition in terms of
614 biopolymers distribution. Thus, while the conversion of holocellulose over this material
615 proceeds largely through the removal of CO₂ and CO, the transformation of lignin occurs
616 mainly through dehydration reactions.

617

618 Fig. 7. Catalytic deoxygenation selectivity (A) and energy yield distribution (B) in the
619 catalytic pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue.

620 The distribution of the chemical energy yield among the different products in the catalytic
621 tests is illustrated in Fig. 7B, being compared with that of the thermal experiment. As
622 occurred with the mass yield, the energy yield of the bio-oil* fraction decreases with the
623 catalyst load although with a less pronounced trend. Thus, while more than 50% of the
624 bio-oil* mass yield was lost with the technical catalyst at the highest C/B ratio, the
625 decrease in the bio-oil* energy yield was about 34% in respect to the value corresponding
626 to the thermal pyrolysis bio-oil. This energy is transferred to gaseous components (CO,
627 light hydrocarbons and hydrogen), as well as to the carbonaceous residue deposited on
628 the catalyst. In this way, the energy contained in the coke formed over the catalyst for the
629 test performed at the highest C/B ratio represents 11.4% of the total chemical energy of
630 the raw biomass. This finding evidences the relevance of minimising the coke formation
631 in terms of energy yield, as well as to attenuate the catalyst deactivation.

632 The previous results denote that improving the bio-oil* properties involve a significant
633 penalty in terms of mass and energy. The efficiency of this upgrading process can be
634 assessed through the relationship between the oxygen content and the yield of the bio-
635 oil* fraction. In this way, Fig. 8A and B show the variation of the bio-oil* deoxygenation
636 degree versus the mass and energy yields, respectively, taking as reference the oxygen
637 content and the yields corresponding to the bio-oil* obtained in the thermal tests. In terms
638 of mass (Fig. 8A), an almost linear variation is observed as the C/B ratio is increased over
639 the technical catalyst.

640

641 Fig. 8. Catalytic bio-oil* deoxygenation degree versus bio-oil* mass (A) and energy (B)
 642 yields (referenced to those of the thermal bio-oil*).

643 However, the relationship between the deoxygenation degree and the energy yield (Fig.
 644 8B) follows a non-linear trend in the initial part of the curve, i.e. during the first stages of
 645 transformation of the pyrolysis vapours over the catalyst. On the other hand, it can be
 646 observed how the ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP catalyst leads to a more efficient bio-oil*
 647 upgrading than the parent n-ZSM-5, this effect being more clearly appreciated regarding
 648 the energy yield. Thus, for the tests performed at C/B = 0.2, the technical catalyst leads
 649 to both higher bio-oil* deoxygenation degree and energy yield in comparison with the
 650 parent n-ZSM-5. A similar behaviour was earlier observed when using wheat straw as
 651 raw biomass in the pyrolysis tests [44]. These results confirm the positive effect of the
 652 ZrO₂ and attapulgite incorporation to the ZSM-5 zeolite, providing this material with a
 653 right combination of acid-base properties. It must be highlighted that for the highest C/B
 654 ratio, the bio-oil* so obtained contains little oxygen (about 10 wt.%), while retaining 48%
 655 and 66% of the mass and energy yield, respectively, in respect to the thermal bio-oil*
 656 fraction.

657 In Fig. 9A and B, the effect of the addition of the catalyst, as well as of the catalyst load,
 658 on the yield and concentration, respectively, of the GC-MS quantified species is
 659 disclosed. The overall concentration of the GC-MS detected components in the thermal
 660 bio-oil* is about 17 wt.%, increasing up to 24 wt.% in the case of the catalytic pyrolysis
 661 test with n-ZSM-5. Interestingly, a quite higher concentration of GC-MS detected species
 662 (42 wt.%) is obtained when using the technical catalyst with C/B = 0.2 w/w. Accordingly,
 663 the technical catalyst allows increasing the concentration in bio-oil* of GC-MS detected

664 compounds, which are the most valuable for commercial applications, by a factor of 2.5
 665 regarding the thermal test. These findings denote the important role of the zeolite-based
 666 catalysts as to reduce the content of oligomeric and heavy compounds in bio-oil*, this
 667 effect being quite more pronounced for the $ZrO_2/n-ZSM-5-ATP$ probably due to the
 668 balanced combination of acid-base properties in this material. Nevertheless, increasing
 669 the B/C ratio over the technical catalyst causes a progressive reduction of both the yield
 670 and concentration of GC-MS detected components due to their transformation into
 671 gaseous species and coke with the advance of the deoxygenation process.

672

673

674 Fig. 9. Total and GC-MS detected (white striped pattern) bio-oil* mass yield (A), overall
 675 concentration of GC-MS detected components (B), concentration of main compound
 676 families (C) and concentration of oxygenated aromatics subfamilies (D) in the bio-oils*.

677 Additional information about the composition of the bio-oil* obtained in the catalytic
 678 tests is provided in Table 6 and Fig. 9C-D. While the parent n-ZSM-5 zeolite induces just
 679 small variations in the different families, the technical catalyst provokes sharp changes in
 680 the bio-oil* product distribution, leading to a remarkable increase in the concentration of

681 most families (AC, LO, FUR and OAR). Thus, when working at $C/B = 0.2$ with the
 682 technical catalyst, the concentration of OAR in bio-oil* reaches 24 wt.%, followed by AC
 683 (mainly acetic acid) and LO with about 9 wt.% and 4 wt,% concentrations, respectively.
 684 Just in the case of SUG, the concentration decreases, becoming negligible, over the
 685 technical catalyst, which shows the high catalytic activity of the latter for the conversion
 686 of levoglucosan. Moreover, some aromatic hydrocarbons (mainly alkyl-naphthalenes and
 687 some alkyl-benzenes, Table 6) are detected in the bio-oil* obtained with this catalyst,
 688 although in a small concentration.

689 Table 6. Concentration of main compounds detected by GC-MS analysis in catalytic bio-
 690 oils*.

Family	C_i (wt.%)	TP 600/450	CP-ZC (C/B=0.2)	CP-TZC (C/B=0.2)	CP-TZC (C/B=0.4)	CP-TZC (C/B=0.8)
AC	Acetic acid	2.19	4.01	8.37	7.69	4.25
	Propanoic acid	0.31	0.37	0.70	0.81	0.40
LO	2-Propanone, 1-hydroxy-	0.31	1.09	1.52	1.07	0.19
	2-Cyclopenten-1-one	0.00	0.54	0.71	0.78	0.61
FUR	Furfural	0.22	0.03	0.11	0.10	0.00
	2(5H)-Furanone	0.18	0.05	1.96	0.21	0.00
PHE	Phenol	0.17	0.32	0.60	0.83	1.63
	p-cresol	0.24	0.10	0.40	0.53	1.06
GUA	Guaiacol	0.53	0.49	1.36	1.45	0.87
	Isoeugenol	0.78	0.10	1.29	1.31	0.93
OAR	Creosol	0.54	0.58	1.51	1.63	1.25
	Syringol	0.97	1.26	3.49	2.76	1.52
SYR	Phenol, 2,6-dimethoxy-4-(2-propenyl)-	1.20	0.87	2.59	1.84	0.53
CAT	1,2-Benzenediol, 3-methoxy-	0.43	0.44	0.90	0.83	0.72
	Catechol	0.15	0.75	0.80	1.05	1.59
METH	1,2,4-Trimethoxybenzene	0.87	0.90	1.98	1.60	0.87
SUG	Levoglucosan	3.09	2.36	0.00	0.00	0.00
AR	BTX	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.07	0.10
	Other alkyl benzenes	0.00	0.11	0.21	0.64	0.70
	Alkyl naphthalenes	0.00	0.08	0.16	0.55	1.46

691 These results are in agreement with the above-commented enhancement in the yield of
 692 GC-MS detected components over $ZrO_2/n-ZSM-5-ATP$. Within the OAR family (Fig.
 693 9D), the highest concentrations correspond with GUA and SYR compounds (about 8

694 wt.% at C/B = 0.2), whereas the other subgroups (PHE, CAT and METH) are present
695 with lower, but noticeable, concentrations (c.a. 2 - 3 wt.%). These findings confirm the
696 ability of this catalyst to transform oligomers and heavy species and, in particular, those
697 related to lignin, which are converted into oxygenated aromatics, mainly of the GUA and
698 SYR families.

699 Regular trends are observed in the concentration of the different families when increasing
700 the C/B ratio over the technical catalyst. In general, for most families the concentration
701 tends to decrease with the C/B ratio in line with the reduction in the overall yield of GC-
702 MS detected components, as above indicated, due to the occurrence of deoxygenation,
703 severe cracking and coke formation reaction. Nevertheless, the concentration of LO
704 remains almost constant with the C/B ratio, whereas that of aromatic hydrocarbons is
705 increased. FUR tend to disappear with the increase of the C/B ratio, probably due to their
706 participation in the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons by Diels-Alder condensation with
707 light olefins [52]. The occurrence of this pathway is confirmed by the rising yield of AR
708 observed with the increment of the catalyst load. Within the OAR family, phenolic
709 compounds significantly grow with the C/B ratio to the detriment of the concentration of
710 guaiacols, syringols and methoxybenzenes.

711 **4. Conclusions**

712 The thermochemical valorisation of a lignin-rich residue, coming from the
713 chemical/biological fractionation of lignocellulose, has been evaluated by thermal and
714 catalytic pyrolysis. For the latter, a technical catalyst, prepared by modification of ZSM-
715 5 zeolite by impregnation with ZrO₂ and agglomeration with attapulgite (ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-
716 ATP), has been used, comparing its performance with that of the parent zeolite.

717 Varying the pyrolysis temperature in the thermal tests between 500 and 650 °C led to a
718 reduction in the char production and increased the volatiles yield of the gaseous and liquid
719 fractions. However, when working at temperatures above 600 °C, a decrease in the
720 production of bio-oil* (bio-oil in water-free basis) was observed in favour of the gaseous
721 fraction, due to the occurrence of severe cracking reactions. The composition of the bio-
722 oil* underwent slight changes due to the effect of temperature, both in its molecular
723 composition and at the elemental level, decreasing its O concentration. The GC-MS
724 quantified bio-oil* components at all temperatures in the thermal tests just represented a
725 small portion of the total liquid organic fraction, either in terms of mass (≈ 10 wt.%) or

726 energy yield ($\approx 12\%$), showing the relevance of the formation of oligomers and heavy
727 species when using a lignin-rich feedstock in the pyrolysis process.

728 The utilisation of a technical catalyst $ZrO_2/n\text{-ZSM-5-ATP}$ and the variation of the
729 catalyst/biomass (C/B) ratio had notable effects on the yield of the different fractions as
730 well as on the elemental and molecular composition of the bio-oil*. The progressive
731 increase of the catalyst load provoked a decrease in the bio-oil* yields, caused by
732 deoxygenation, severe cracking and coking reactions. However, the elemental
733 composition of the bio-oil* fraction improved remarkably with the C/B ratio, being
734 largely enriched in C, while the O concentration was reduced up to 10 wt.%. Compared
735 with the parent n-ZSM-5 zeolite, the technical catalyst was more efficient for bio-oil*
736 deoxygenation, which took place mainly by dehydration reactions, although with an
737 increasing share of decarboxylation and decarbonylation at higher C/B ratios.

738 Another remarkable effect of the technical catalyst was its capability of increasing the
739 concentration of GC-MS detected species in bio-oil*, sharply reducing the content of
740 oligomeric and heavy compounds. Thus, while the concentration of GC-MS detected
741 components in the thermal bio-oil* was just 17 wt.%, it was enhanced up to 42 wt.%
742 when using the technical catalyst at C/B = 0.2. This finding shows the strong bio-oil*
743 upgrading effect caused by the ZSM-5 based technical catalyst, even when operating
744 under mild reaction conditions in the catalytic bed.

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